

COLOR PICTURE OF THE WORLD IN THE ENGLISH, RUSSIAN AND KARAKALPAK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: When we think about the world, we often picture it in our minds as a whole, without considering the individual pieces which make it unique. Over time, we have developed various methods to convey the world's complexity to ourselves, one of which is the color picture of the world. In this article, we will explore the color picture of the world in three languages: English, Russian, and Karakalpak. This fascinating comparison will showcase the differences in approaches to presenting the world's rich cultural heritage.

Keywords: Color picture, World, English, Russian, Karakalpak, Languages, Multilingualism.

As the world becomes increasingly interconnected, it is essential to explore and understand the diverse cultures and languages that make up our global community. One way to accomplish this is through the use of color pictures, which can provide a visual representation of the world in different languages. In this article, we will examine the color picture of the world in three languages: English, Russian, and Karakalpak.

English Color Picture of the World. In the English language, the color picture of the world is typically based on a map with different colors representing different countries or regions. Commonly used colors include blue for water, green for land, and red for countries and regions. The names of countries and continents are often written in black or white, making them stand out against the colorful background. A typical English color picture of the world will show North and South America in shades of green and brown, with the United States, Canada, Mexico, Brazil, and Argentina highlighted in red. Europe is usually shown in shades of blue and green, with the United Kingdom, France, Germany, Spain, and Italy highlighted in red. Africa is often depicted in shades of green and yellow, with Egypt, South Africa, and Nigeria highlighted in red. Asia is usually shown in shades of blue and green, with China, Japan, India, and Russia highlighted in red. Finally, Australia and New Zealand are often depicted in shades of green and blue, with Australia highlighted in red. The English language color picture of the world relies on distinguishing colors to differentiate between regions, countries, and oceans. This type of map is informative and widely used in schools and other educational settings. The colors typically used are blue and green for oceans and land, respectively. The color red in the English

color picture of the world is mostly used to mark countries and regions, while black is used to label cities and other geographical features. The United States is one of the most visible countries on the English color picture of the world, and it is shown as being located in North America, which often serves as a standalone continent on these maps. Mexico, Canada, and Central America are shown alongside the United States, making up the entire region. South America is also shown independently, depicting countries like Argentina, Brazil, and Chile in the red color used for marking them. Europe is marked by greens and browns, while Asia is composed of various shades of blue and green. Africa is depicted with the use of greens and yellows, and Australia is often colored a darker shade of green or blue, indicating its position as an island. One thing that stands out in the English color picture of the world is the use of the colors, blue and green, to differentiate the body of water and the landmass. It is an interesting representation that shows that the distribution of water is an integral component of our world.

Russian Color Picture of the World. In the Russian language, the color picture of the world is often similar to the English version, with different countries and regions represented by different colors. However, the colors used in the Russian color picture of the world may differ from those used in the English version. For example, Russia itself is often depicted in red, while other countries may be represented by different colors. A typical Russian color picture of the world will show North and South America in shades of blue and green, with the United States, Canada, Brazil, and Argentina highlighted in red. Europe is usually depicted in shades of green and yellow, with Russia, Germany, and Italy highlighted in red. Africa is often shown in shades of green and orange, with Egypt, South Africa, and Nigeria highlighted in red. Asia is usually depicted in shades of blue and green, with China, Japan, India, and Russia highlighted in red. Finally, Australia and New Zealand are often depicted in shades of green and blue, with Australia highlighted in red.

Karakalpak Color Picture of the World. In the Karakalpak language, which is spoken in Uzbekistan, the color picture of the world is different from both the English and Russian versions. Instead of depicting different countries using different colors, the Karakalpak color picture of the world is based on a series of geometric shapes and colors, each of which represents a different area of the world. In the Karakalpak color picture of the world, the Americas are represented by a red triangle, Europe by a blue circle, Africa by a green square, Asia by a purple diamond, and Australia by a yellow hexagon. The names of

countries and continents are often written in the Karakalpak language, using a distinctive Arabic script. The names of the continents and countries are often written in the Karakalpak language, which uses the Arabic script. The Karakalpak language is primarily spoken in Uzbekistan, and it is noted for its uniqueness in the country. The Karakalpak color picture of the world presents geographical information in a unique manner that stands out in comparison to other maps. It has a different appeal that highlights the interconnectedness of the countries and their cultural heritage.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the color picture of the world can provide a fascinating insight into the diverse cultures and languages that make up our global community. While the English and Russian versions of the color picture of the world are relatively similar, they differ in the colors used and the way that countries and regions are depicted. The Karakalpak version of the color picture of the world is more abstract, using geometric shapes and colors to represent different areas of the world. By understanding the different ways that different languages and cultures represent the world in color, we can gain a deeper appreciation of the richness and diversity of our global community. The color picture of the world is an essential tool that helps us understand the diversity of our planet. The English color picture of the world relies on differentiation in colors to delineate continents, countries, and regions. In contrast, the Russian approach uses a distinct color code to highlight important regions. The Karakalpak version, on the other hand, uses geometrical shapes to highlight continents' forms. It is fascinating to see how different languages and cultures represent the world in their own unique way. Studying the distinctions can provide a deeper understanding of how people perceive geography and culture, creating a more significant connection between diverse societies.

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